

2015/											
nonBT											
Bloco1			bloco2			bloco 3					

node	category	functional.group	level	M	N	B	M	N	B	M	N	B
Agallia albidula	invertebrate	herbivore	2	0.001286		5 0.0064286	0.000514286		4 0.0020571	0.001029		11 0.0113143
Allograpta obliqua	invertebrate	predator	3	0.018357		6 0.1101429	0.022028571		7 0.1542	0.011014		6 0.0660857
Anthonomus grandis	invertebrate	herbivore	2	0.0492		29 1.4268	0.0697		37 2.5789	0.0656		31 2.0336
Aphis gossypii	invertebrate	herbivore	2	0.006		331 1.986	0.0075		229 1.7175	0.00575		83 0.47725
Astylus variegatus	invertebrate	herbivore	2	0.060429		15 0.9064286	0.073857143		23 1.6987143	0.040286		15 0.6042857
Atta robusta	invertebrate	herbivore	2	0		0 0	0.001257143		67 0.0842286	0.001257		2 0.0025143
Bemisia tabaci	invertebrate	herbivore	2	0.009326		6511 60.719726	0.009325714		7432 69.308709	0.009131		9148 83.534309
Bracon vulgaris	invertebrate	parasitoid	3	0.000343		3 0.0010286	0.000514286		3 0.0015429	0.000514		4 0.0020571
Catolaccus grandis	invertebrate	parasitoid	3	0.000446		1 0.0004457	0.000445714		10 0.0044571	0.000891		5 0.0044571
Chrysoperla externa	invertebrate	predator	3	0.029371		23 0.6755429	0.008815714		19 0.1674986	0.008816		16 0.1410514
Cycloneda sanguinea	invertebrate	predator	3	0		0 0	0.031371429		7 0.2196	0.005229		1 0.0052286
Condylostylus longicornis	invertebrate	predator	3	0.0096		30 0.288	0.008		11 0.088	0.008		18 0.144
Diabrotica speciosa	invertebrate	herbivore	2	0.003657		1 0.0036571	0.014628571		4 0.0585143	0.003657		1 0.0036571
Doru luteipes	invertebrate	predator	4	0.0045		1 0.0045	0.009		2 0.018	0.0045		1 0.0045
Dysdercus ruficollis	invertebrate	herbivore	2	0.0133		1 0.0133	0.0133		2 0.0266	0		0 0
Empoasca kraemeri	invertebrate	herbivore	2	0.0044		34 0.1496	0.005028571		38 0.1910857	0.003771		29 0.1093714
Eriopis connexa	invertebrate	predator	3	0.001729		1 0.0017286	0.006914286		5 0.0345714	0.005186		4 0.0207429
Euschistus heros	invertebrate	herbivore	2	0.1325		9 1.1925	0.056785714		3 0.1703571	0.075714		4 0.3028571
Euxesta stigmatias	invertebrate	detritivore	0	0.001129		1 0.0011286	0.004514286		4 0.0180571	0		0 0
Frankliniella schultzei	invertebrate	herbivore	2	0		0 0	7.14286E-05		3 0.0002143	3.57E-05		2 7.143E-05
Gossypium hirsutum	producer	producer	1	3716.926		65 241600.17	4167.072857		65 270859.74	4031.729		65 262062.36
Harmonia axyridis	invertebrate	predator	3	0.005857		1 0.0058571	0.005857143		2 0.0117143	0		0 0
Hipodamia convergens	invertebrate	predator	3	0.011543		2 0.0230857	0.005771429		2 0.0115429	0.005771		1 0.0057714
Horcia nobilelus	invertebrate	herbivore	2	0.002343		2 0.0046857	0.003514286		3 0.0105429	0		0 0
Neomegalotomus parvus	invertebrate	herbivore	2	0.003771		6 0.0226286	0.001257143		1 0.0012571	0.002514		3 0.0075429
Orius insidiosus	invertebrate	predator	3	0.000314		1 0.0003143	0.001571429		10 0.0157143	0		0 0
Pachyneuron aphidis	invertebrate	parasitoid	3	0		0 0	0		0 0	0		0 0
Repipta flavicans	invertebrate	predator	4	0.013657		1 0.0136571	0		0 0	0		0 0

2016															
BT									nonBT						
Bloco1			bloco2			bloco 3			Bloco1			bloco2			
M	N	B	M	N	B	M	N	B	M	N	B	M	N	B	
0.0015429		10	0.0154286	0.0023143		31	0.0717429	0.0025714	12	0.0308571	0	0	0	0	
0.0073429		3	0.0220286	0.0146857		7	0.1028	0.0183571	29	0.5323571	0.0214167	7	0.1499167	0.0257	
0.0615		32	1.968	0.0656		49	3.2144	0.0492	22	1.0824	0.1339333	72	9.6432	0.12915	
0.00625		225	1.40625	0.00675		366	2.4705	0.0045	255	1.1475	0.004375	74	0.32375	0.0055417	
0.0402857		8	0.3222857	0.1342857		50	6.7142857	0.0671429	17	1.1414286	0	0	0	0	
0		0	0	0		0	0	0	0	0	0.0022	3	0.0066	0.0044	
0.0097143		6963	67.640571	0.0099086		4842	47.977303	0.0093257	5130	47.840914	0.0124667	7290	90.882	0.0113333	
0.0008571		6	0.0051429	0.0010286		6	0.0061714	0.0006857	4	0.0027429	0.001	5	0.005	0.0002	
0.0011143		6	0.0066857	0.0002229		8	0.0017829	0.0004457	14	0.00624	0.00026	1	0.00026	0	
0.00561		11	0.06171	0.0088157		19	0.1674986	0.0080143	14	0.1122	0.010285	26	0.26741	0.012155	
0.0209143		5	0.1045714	0.0156857		3	0.0470571	0.0261429	16	0.4182857	0.0061	1	0.0061	0.0122	
0.0064		11	0.0704	0.0104		63	0.6552	0.012	21	0.252	0.0018667	1	0.0018667	0	
0.0109714		3	0.0329143	0.0036571		1	0.0036571	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0042667	
0.0045		11	0.0495	0.0045		1	0.0045	0.0135	4	0.054	0	0	0	0	
0.0931		10	0.931	0.0665		12	0.798	0.0798	12	0.9576	0.0775833	10	0.7758333	0.1241333	
0.0062857		95	0.5971429	0.0075429		135	1.0182857	0.0056571	73	0.4129714	0.0025667	11	0.0282333	0.0025667	
0.0017286		1	0.0017286	0.0034571		2	0.0069143	0	0	0	0.0080667	4	0.0322667	0.0040333	
0.0378571		2	0.0757143	0.0189286		1	0.0189286	0.0189286	1	0.0189286	0.0441667	2	0.0883333	0.0220833	
0		0	0	0.0033857		4	0.0135429	0.0011286	1	0.0011286	0.0026333	2	0.0052667	0.0065833	
3.571E-05		1	3.571E-05	0		0	0	0	0	0	0.00025	6	0.0015	4.167E-05	
3347.83		65	217608.95	3615.5071		65	235007.96	3381.9157	65	219824.52	3209.0817	52	166872.25	3905.53	
0.0058571		1	0.0058571	0.0058571		1	0.0058571	0.0058571	1	0.0058571	0	0	0	0	
0		0	0	0		0	0	0.0173143	3	0.0519429	0.0336667	6	0.202	0.0134667	
0.0070286		12	0.0843429	0.0058571		7	0.041	0.0023429	2	0.0046857	0	0	0	0	
0.0037714		5	0.0188571	0.0050286		8	0.0402286	0.0037714	4	0.0150857	0.0014667	1	0.0014667	0	
0.0015714		6	0.0094286	0.0003143		1	0.0003143	0.0009429	5	0.0047143	0.0003667	1	0.0003667	0	
0		0	0	0		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
0.0273143		2	0.0546286	0.0273143		4	0.1092571	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	

2016/2017

BT

bloco 3

Bloco1

bloco2

bloco 3

M	N	B	M	N	B	M	N	B	M	N	B	
0.0003		1	0.0003	0.0006	2	0.0012	0	0	0	0.0003	1	0.0003
0.0257		6	0.1542	0.0171333	21	0.3598	0.0085667	4	0.0342667	0.0085667	4	0.0342667
0.0956667		38	3.6353333	0.0861	35	3.0135	0.1195833	54	6.4575	0.1195833	58	6.9358333
0.0046667		54	0.252	0.00525	235	1.23375	0.0064167	104	0.6673333	0.0040833	134	0.5471667
0		0	0	0	0	0	0.0078333	1	0.0078333	0	0	0
0.0022		6	0.0132	0.0022	9	0.0198	0.0051333	13	0.0667333	0.0036667	8	0.0293333
0.01088	5668	61.66784	0.0106533	8358	89.04056	0.0111067	6738	74.83672	0.01156	6221	71.91476	
0.0006		6	0.0036	0.0004	2	0.0008	0.0002	1	0.0002	0.0002	1	0.0002
0		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0.00748		14	0.10472	0.00935	19	0.17765	0.00935	10	0.0935	0.014025	29	0.406725
0.0183		5	0.0915	0.0122	2	0.0244	0.0122	2	0.0244	0.0305	12	0.366
0.0037333		4	0.0149333	0.0018667	2	0.0037333	0.0018667	3	0.0056	0.0028	3	0.0084
0.0042667		1	0.0042667	0	0	0	0.0042667	1	0.0042667	0.0085333	2	0.0170667
0		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.00525	1	0.00525
0.1862		44	8.1928	0.0310333	3	0.0931	0.0155167	1	0.0155167	0.1241333	13	1.6137333
0.0040333		14	0.0564667	0.0029333	9	0.0264	0.0036667	22	0.0806667	0.0047667	21	0.1001
0.00605		3	0.01815	0.0040333	3	0.0121	0.0040333	4	0.0161333	0.0040333	2	0.0080667
0.0441667		2	0.0883333	0.0441667	2	0.0883333	0.0441667	5	0.2208333	0.0220833	1	0.0220833
0.0079		10	0.079	0.0052667	5	0.0263333	0.0052667	4	0.0210667	0.0092167	8	0.0737333
8.333E-05		3	0.00025	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3487.3333		54	188316	2834.3533	55	155889.43	1907.4433	56	106816.83	3033.355	51	154701.11
0		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0.0404		9	0.3636	0.0336667	8	0.2693333	0.0336667	6	0.202	0	0	0
0		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0.0014667		2	0.0029333	0	0	0	0.0014667	1	0.0014667	0.0029333	2	0.0058667
0.0003667		1	0.0003667	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0		5	0	0	4	0	0	6	0	0	0	0
0		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0011167	1	0.0011167